

Teachers' and Students' Roles in Reducing Foreign Language Anxiety

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Abstract

Foreign language anxiety is a common challenge faced by English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners worldwide. This review paper explores effective strategies for removing foreign language anxiety among EFL learners. The analysis of published resources revealed several major themes, including the role of teachers, and students. Regarding teachers, they are recommend to implanting different classroom activities, and student-centred learning approaches, clear instructions, creating a relaxing classroom environment, teachers' psychological aspects, and the incorporation of technology. Students also play an important in reducing their foreign language anxiety Overall, this review highlights the significance of effective strategies in removing foreign language anxiety among EFL learners. By implementing these strategies, teachers can create a supportive and conducive learning environment that promotes language learning and reduces anxiety among learners. Students play a crucial role in reducing foreign language anxiety when learning English as a second or foreign language. They can take proactive steps to identify and address their personal and interpersonal anxieties, employing positive thinking strategies, avoidance strategy, and role of family help students overcoming their classroom anxiety.

Keywords: *Foreign language anxiety, EFL learners, language learning, language anxiety reduction strategies, teachers' role.*

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Introduction

Foreign language anxiety negatively impacts the quality of learning and is a critical factor in a learner's success or failure in learning a foreign language (Alrabai, 2015; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991). Reducing students' language anxiety can enhance students overall learning experience and improve motivation and achievement. Indeed, understanding and utilizing standard and effective strategies for elimination of foreign language anxiety is very crucial for both EFL /ESL teachers and students while teaching and learning the English language since they are helpful in overcoming FLA in the classroom and later help them have strong command in English language. In

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short, teachers and students are obliged to understanding all the techniques, strategies and approaches that help them reduce foreign language anxiety.

There are numerous obstacles preventing students from communicating effectively. One of the most important factors that have an adverse impact on language learning is foreign language anxiety (R. Oxford, 1990). Anxiety has been identified as an important factor affecting the learning of foreign languages (Liu, 2012). Foreign language learning anxiety is described as fear or apprehension that occurs when a learner is expected to use the second or foreign language (MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991). Anxiety employs a significant influence on learning. It sets of overwhelming negative emotions which can prevail over rational thinking, as a result of which learners are not able to concentrate on the task and process as many pieces of information as normally, which leads to poorer performance (Hembree, 1988). Hence, it has a negative impact on both short- and long-term memory, and has an effect on motivation. Anxious learners are not likely to crave for education as they associate the classroom situation with a fear that is hard to overcome. Many theories gained from different avenues have been proposed to explain what causes the language anxiety and what variables may affect it, and more importantly, how to cope with it (Cooper et al., 2018).

Based on the current literature, throughout the world several studies are conducted on strategies that eliminate foreign language anxiety among EFL/ESL learners. The most common ones are: communication, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation, classroom activities, friendly atmosphere of the classroom, cooperative learning, clear instruction, pace of speech from teachers, self-concept of competence, teachers' behavior, classroom management, Learner's autonomy, Identify anxious learners, uses of technology in the classroom (Abdurahman et al., 2018; Aida, 1994; Alcala, 2002; Anandari, 2015; Atifnigar, Zaheer, et al., 2020; Atifnigar et al., 2021, 2022; Brown, 2000; Cinkara, 2016; Fuller, 1978; Grant et al., 2014; Hashemi, 2011; Horwitz et al., 1986; Ismail, 2016; Johnson, 2006; Mejias et al., 1991; Nagahashi, 2007; Otieno et al., 2016; Pappamihiel, 2002; Paradowski et al., 2015; Ratanasiripong et al., 2010; Saunders & Crookall, 1985; Shams, 2005; Siagto-Wakat, 2017; Tanveer, 2007; Tonks et al., 2013; Underwood, 2012; Von Worde, 2003; Walton, 1981; Woodrow, 2006; Young, 1990).

Plethora of studies conducted on the impacts of foreign language anxiety among learners. However, limited investigations are carried out on reducing foreign language anxiety which is considered as insufficient antidote for language teachers and students which are too dispersed data. Therefore, After critically analyzing published resources in regard to the strategies eliminating foreign language anxiety FLA among ELS/EFL learners we have found two major themes namely teachers' and students role in eliminating foreign language anxiety among learners which are described in the following passages.

Literature Review

FLA is the nervousness that can occur when learning a new language or a complex set of self-perceptions, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors associated with classroom language learning due to the unique nature of language acquisition (Horwitz et al., 1986). FLA is the experience of worrying and feeling negative emotions while learning a second language (Lucas et al., 2011; MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991). FLA is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that involves various aspects of self-perception, beliefs,

emotions, and behaviors related to foreign language classroom learning (Horwitz et al., 1986). On the other hand, FLA is a complex phenomenon influenced by multiple factors, including students' personality, beliefs about language learning held by learners and teachers, the teacher-student relationship, classroom environment, and testing. Each individual experiences a unique level of language apprehension and expresses it differently. Various strategies can be employed to address inhibitions related to speaking in a foreign language, depending on the specific factors that trigger them (Benamara & Behlhadj, 2022).

This study discusses various types of anxieties related to FLA, including situational anxiety, social anxiety, trait anxiety, and state anxiety. Situational anxiety specifically pertains to anxiety experienced consistently within a particular environment or situation over time. Social anxiety is primarily triggered in social and communicative contexts and encompasses affective, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions. Trait anxiety is a more pervasive form of anxiety that occurs across various situations and is connected to an individual's personality. State anxiety is a temporary feeling of tension that arises in unfamiliar situations and dissipates after the situation concludes, such as delivering a public speech (MacIntyre & Gardner, 1991).

Components of Foreign Language Anxiety

The influential theory of foreign language learning anxiety, developed by Horwitz et al. (1986), identifies three key components: communication apprehension, test anxiety, and fear of negative evaluation. Communication apprehension refers to the unease or fear experienced when engaging in real or anticipated communication with others. It stems from the feeling of being unable to express ideas or thoughts accurately (Kao & Craigie, 2013; Mejias et al., 1991). Communication apprehension can manifest in two ways. Firstly, it can manifest as oral communication anxiety, which includes experiences like stage fright or struggling to speak in group settings. Secondly, it can manifest as receiver anxiety, which involves difficulties in listening to or learning a spoken language. In a classroom environment, these apprehensions tend to be heightened due to constant monitoring of language performance and the learners' limited control over the language situation (Horwitz et al., 1986).

Test anxiety, also known as apprehension over academic performance, is primarily driven by a fear of failure (Cakici, 2016; Sarason et al., 1972). Anxious learners often have unrealistic expectations of themselves, perceiving anything less than a flawless performance as a failure (Horwitz et al., 1986). In a foreign language class, where tests and quizzes are frequent, even the most intelligent and well-prepared student can make mistakes, let alone those who experience anxiety (Cohen & Norst, 1989). Research has indicated that competitiveness in tests and anxiety are linked to individuals' self-esteem. When students receive low scores in foreign language courses, it can negatively impact their self-esteem.

The third component of foreign language learning anxiety is the fear of negative evaluation. Unlike test anxiety, this type of anxiety is not limited to test-taking situations. It extends to any social evaluative situation, such as speaking in a foreign language class or attending a job interview. In a foreign language class, where evaluations are ongoing, learners can be particularly sensitive to the evaluations of their peers and teachers. They may feel apprehensive about situations where others might mock their language abilities. As a result, some learners may develop anxiety regarding the evaluations from their teachers or peers and may even try to avoid such evaluative situations (Nijat et al., 2019; Watson & Friend, 1969).

Discussion

Strategies for Removing Foreign Language Anxiety

After investigating numerous publications in regards to “reducing”, “elimination”, “removing”, “copping”, “alleviation”, and “dealing” with foreign language anxiety among EFL learners, then the following major themes, and codes (see figure 1) are discovered to represent effective strategies that play a vital role in removing foreign language anxiety among EFL learners throughout the world:

Figure 1. Reducing Foreign Language Anxiety Diagram

Teachers' Role

One of the major themes that discovered after analysis of published resources was the teacher's role in eliminating foreign language anxiety among EFL learners from different context. Indeed, teacher can tackle foreign language among learners in different ways namely classroom activities, implementation of student centered learning approach, and teacher's psychological behavior in the classroom which are described below.

Classroom Activities

Teachers are required to exploit diverse classroom activities in the classroom in order to eliminate foreign language anxiety among EFL learners since student become more interested in learning English as a foreign language. Teachers should different classroom activities to removes FLA anxiety among elf learners, it is mentioned in the literature that teachers should aware themselves of some of the teaching reference of their learners and use various activities and practices during the classroom (Von Worde, 2003).

Teachers can implement activities that involve drama in which students feel free and communicate effectively without any anxiousness (Tanveer, 2007). Specifically, in regards to the speaking, there are some strategies such as repair English speaking in the classroom which can be used to remove its anxiety. In addition, individual practices such as memorizing of some key word and phrase, peer activities, outdoor activities which called drama rehearsals, and watching a short video clip and later perform that through drama (Anandari, 2015). Teachers may also utilize agony columns, ghost revenger, mistakes panel, anxious photos, reversed accents, and trigger picture activities to cope with FLA among EFL learners (R. L. Oxford et al., 1989).

Moreover, researchers suggest that within classroom activities, implementation of role play is an effective antidote for elimination of FLA, particularly in speaking skill (Hashemi, 2011; Paradowski et al., 2015). Creating graph in the classroom remove students anxiety in which they illustrate their level of stress they faces in different stages of speaking activities and later they can compare their stress and notice their anxiety and gradually remove them (Samad et al., 2020). Similarly, teacher alleviate students FLA in the classroom through using graph anxiety to sow the highest level of students anxiety and provide supplementary material to supports student interaction in the classroom (Atifnigar, Alokozay, Wahidullah, Zaheer, et al., 2020; Atifnigar, Hasanzoy, et al., 2020; Atifnigar & Alokozay, 2020; Paradowski et al., 2015). It is also recommended that teachers should use language related games for example solving a problem in target language can enhance student's courage and practice in the classroom activities (Marković, 2016).

Finally, pair works and group works also cope with foreign language anxiety. While students are involved in group work activities they show their low level of anxiety when compared to the speaking in front of the classroom (Kirkgöz, 2009). In this regard, language related activities such as peer work, personal discussion are considered as a less stressful activity when used in the language classroom and students can easily from each other. Cooperative learning is considered as an effective strategy in eliminating FLA along with provision of non-threatening and supporting context in which learners feel lower stress when interacting with partners (Nagahashi, 2007).

Student-Centered Learning Approach SCL

When teachers teach English as a second or foreign language, they need to be well familiar with 21th century learning skills, particularly they have to teach the students with student-centered learning approach since it involves students to work practically inside the classroom and only the teacher work as moderator, supporter, facilitator and guide. In line with this, teacher should lead the class as the facilitator which make a student-centered learning class in which learners can improve their critical thinking, problem solving, sharing knowledge with others and finally improve their public skills (Emaliana, 2017).

Inside student-centered learning approach, teachers are required to have fully understanding of cooperative learning when teaching English language students. Cooperative learning strategy can reduce foreign language anxiety once it is implemented by the teachers in the classroom, in short it can diminish students anxiety when they are involved in small and supportive group of classmates and also teacher should provide enough opportunities for the students produce language as much as possible and increase learning outcome consequently (cited). Cooperative learning strategy is aimed to involve students to perform one task with a group of peers. Actually, this strategy possess several elements namely (1) positive interdependent in which goal possess a common and every member of the group is expected to achieve the goal; (2) face to face group engagement in which members of a group are encouraged to interact, assist others for achievement and learn from each other; (3) solo or group accountability in which a task is divided into different members of the group and each should succeed in their part; creating small groups social skills entailing negotiating and utility of group engagement skills; (5) group processing in which student reflects their perception on group experiences (Antil et al., 1998). Research studies show that students feel less intimidated when working with partners and in small groups (Nagahashi, 2007).

Likewise, teachers are also recommended to using collaborative learning technique inside the language classroom. Hopefully, currently majority of the teachers use this technique in a broad spectrum which is centered on creation of a situation in which learners aggressively cooperate in the classroom activities by sharing their experience and perform different to achieve a learning outcome with fear and anxiety (cited). In short, through collaborative learning and teaching students are involve to perform different activities via group works, discussion, project and some other activities (cited). Also, thorough collaborative learning, students are obliged to share their performance, socialize, support one another, and exchange ideas for the purpose of targeted goals without any anxiety and stress. Therefore, such situation not only pave the way for a harmonious atmosphere in the English language classroom but also help English language instructors to reduce the anxiety of students and graph the focus of their students whey they learn English language (Opfer et al., 2011). (Srinivas, 2019, p. 6). All in all, performing collaborative activities is beneficial to the students' learning process in term of anxiety, self-confidence, and language skills (Govindasamy & Shah, 2020).

Clear Instruction

Clear instruction also helps students overcome language learning anxiety in the classroom. It is claimed that anxiety can be eliminated by providing learners with clear instruction and guidance on carrying out specific task, and the required wording of instruction and also gathering students mistakes and errors and discuss them with in the classroom which alleviate the fear of being negatively evaluation and embarrassed in front of the classroom (Tanveer, 2007). Teachers may also adapt technique of personalizing instruction, meaning when instruction students name each student by their names or object in the classroom through aid of illustration and gesture (Paradowski et al., 2015). In line with this, teachers should use the students name when making questions in the classroom which may help student increase their feeling of self-worth (Prodromou 1994). This may also raise the students' feelings of self-worth. Moreover, teachers are also required to adjust their mood of speech and vocabulary to the level of students through which their anxiety can be lowered (Alcala, 2002). Teachers struggle to have a long lasting communication with native speakers and stay in the country of English speaking through which later helps students to communicate with them and can help students overcoming their anxiety when utter to them in native like pace (Kralova & Tirpakova, 2019).

Relaxing Classroom Environment

Teachers play a supportive role in developing excellent learning environment by providing an effective layout and relaxing environment of the classroom through which foreign language anxiety can be reduced.

First of all, the setting of the classroom may affect students' engagement and may decrease their learning anxiety. Seating and desk arrangement let students to face each other and communicate effectively with each other when performing students and teacher activities that can increase students' emotion of belonging. The proper layout of the classroom increase mutual assistance of students and create a double effect environment. First effect increases the students' cognitive skills through which worried learner may get assistant from unworried students and be prepared for classroom activities. The second effect is the decreases of anxiety among learners in the classroom and worried students may not feel isolation which later can create a positive thinking strategy because confident students are also worried about friend, and there is no need

to be threatened by them (Koba et. al.). Seating arrangement also support an excellent classroom environment in which student can be seated in circle posture and students can face each other and they create class community and promote cooperative learning in which students can improve their problem solving skills and become students may feel relaxing and possess a noncompetitive environment (Joan, 1993).

Secondly, teachers also create a relaxing classroom environment in which student eliminate their foreign language anxiety by providing a relaxing and friendly learning environment to the EFL learners. Actually, teachers play a significant role in diminishing anxiety by catering warm and attractive atmosphere inside the classroom and increase learners' motivation in learning the English language (cite). Teachers are required to help student fight against negative attitudes and unfriendly emotion when learning the English language and they should build learners' self-confidence through using positive reinforcement and motivation (cite). Moreover, it is also imperative that teachers should create a friendly, natural and congruent classroom environment (cite) since a friendly coordination between teachers and student is an important part of the classroom in which students feel less worried. Establishing an individual mood at any time in the process of teaching with optimistic, confident and joyful mood to face the students so that they may feel cheerful and interested in learning the language (cite). Teacher should also understand their student so that they can engagement in the classroom activities and reduce their tension from the teachers and student answer question may assistant decrease anxiety (cite). In addition, there have been various techniques, method and strategies that assistant teachers in reducing foreign language anxiety by providing language environment more affective. For example, the classroom atmosphere should be more friendly where student can make mistakes (cite). All in all, teachers should strive to make the language classroom more friendly, supportive and non-threatening learning condition in which students can build self-confidence and reduce their anxiety (cite).

Teachers' Psychological Aspects

As is it cleared that in most cases student and teachers psychological factors affect both teaching learning process. In language classroom, teachers' psychology also play a crucial role in reducing foreign language anxiety among EFL learners that is why it is suggested that teachers should remove psychosocial problems, motivate students and remove their exam anxiety when teaching English language learners for the purpose of reducing language learning anxiety.

Majority of the researchers claim that teacher should remove students' psychological problems and help them become less anxious in the classroom. In general, teachers should be extremely sensitive, understandable, aware from possibilities of learning, and determine learners who feel anxious in the classroom and provide them strategies and techniques to remove their anxiety so that they can participate more in the classroom (cite). Most of the students failed to perform in front of people is due to some emotion of uncertainty, insecurity, self-reluctance, and anxiety. Therefore, it is imperative that teachers should practice upon students standing and practicing communication in front of people regular, and refrain from correcting students' mistakes and they feel comfortable in the classroom (Boroujeni et al., 2015). It is recommended that teachers should implicitly correct students' mistakes instead they enable them toward self-correction ability (Turula, 2002). Similarly, it is reported that learners in which teachers ask student in publicly which is considered as one of the foreign language anxiety, alternatively call on students in preplanned and predicable way may cause less anxiety in the classroom then being asked randomly(Williams & Andrade, 2008). Teachers

should understand the sources of anxiety rooting from students' personality and later create activities raising students' self-esteem. Finally, teachers should divert students in term of unrealistic expectation about the language process which may avoid them from feeling frustrated and disappointed with carrying out and from thinking of it in term of failure (Young, 1990).

Moreover, in the literature, it also mentioned that teachers play an important role in reducing students' anxiety in the classroom by motivating them. In order to motivate students, teachers are required to give a positive assessment of the learners a humor of accomplishment in which learner anxiety can be reduced too (Na, 2007). Motivating students toward improving their confidence and believes in their capacity to overcome classroom anxiety. Actually, to cater students with a change to have accomplishment in the classroom so that can build up their full confidence and self-esteem, for instance asking limited number of simple question, perform some simple dialogue and other (Zorawski et al., 2005). Teachers, also motivate their students by identifying their anxious learner and regularly providing them activities and interventions to overcome their language anxiety (Aida, 1994) and they must regularly discuss the importance of English language in their daily, academic and professional life through which they can reduce their foreign language anxiety (Yashima, 2002).

Furthermore, one of the major reported foreign language anxiety is the exam related anxiety in which teachers reduce it as a part language anxiety providing different strategies. For examine students, there are different form of assessment and evaluations. First, oral exam which is a part of assessments, teachers' may create a positive and warm behavior cause student to receiving more outcome from the learner oral exam that is why teachers should prefer to use oral exam in which students may feel less anxious (Alrabai, 2015). Teacher must prepare students for exam by familiarize them with format of exam, rubrics and rating criteria, and familiarize them that they firstly assessed. The benefits of informing students in advanced may not frustrate them during exam but actually they will not be surprised and feel anxious instead they will directly solve them easily (Hayes & Read, 2004)

Using Technology

Using technology including digital electronic devices, sot wares, online platforms, and many more in the classroom assist teachers reducing students' foreign language anxiety. Indeed, virtual environment helps students reducing their foreign language anxiety. Initially, every teachers should identify student's anxiety before commencing their classes and later provide different technological facilities to remove students' anxiety. As a matter of fact, teachers can use social media, which excessively predominant among learners (Abdurahman et al., 2018). If teachers feel extremely anxious learners. They can practice uploading their videos with web 2.0 tools such as Google Classroom, YouTube, Edmodo, and other social media platforms in which student can eradicate their anxiety when learning the language (Ghounane, 2020). Video recording is used by the teachers as a tool to record the performance to provide them time to reflect their performance through watching their video (Tripp & Rich, 2012). Teachers can use computerized pronunciation practices such as English language dictionary to improve students pronunciation for better speaking skills (Shams, 2005). Virtual platforms including chats and computer games are considered as the most effective strategies in reducing those that their learning occurs in real world (Grant et al., 2014). It is revealed that through video stimulated recalling strategy student can reflect upon the symptom a cause of foreign language anxiety while speaking and is proved to be an effective tool (Cinkara, 2016). Finally, doodling is also

an important tool in which learners express their daily classroom experiences through which teachers realized the impacts of foreign language anxiety and suit their classes accordingly (Siagto-Wakat, 2017).

Students' Role

Students' roles are important in reducing foreign language anxiety when learning English as a second or foreign language. Following are the common strategies that are delved from literature:

Students themselves play a significant role in detecting their personal and interpersonal anxieties and remove them gradually inside the classroom. There are various techniques that support this strategy, it is assumed that learners name and elaborate their fears, and note them on the board through which they can estimate that they are not the only people who experience such anxiety that is why they feel much more secure among their classmates (Foss and Reitzel, 1988). In addition, when students understand and show their fear and are aware of its irrational consequences which have limited amount in their real life. Therefore, after performing such activity then the students show their eagerness to overcoming their anxiety instead of prohibiting fear-rising condition. In addition, Crookall and Oxford (1991) propose a method called "Agony Column" to overcome personal and interpersonal anxieties. This activity involves writing letters to express fears and problems related to foreign language communication. Participants assume three roles: themselves as anxious students, an "Agony Aunt" who provides advice in response to the letters, and counselors who give their opinions on the advice received. In the first stage, students write letters sharing their anxieties, then in small groups, they discuss and compose appropriate replies to their peers' letters. Finally, the letters are returned to the original recipients, and students reflect in groups on potential solutions to their problems. This activity helps students become aware of their language acquisition-related fears by expressing them in writing and learn effective strategies to cope with these issues. It also creates a sense of solidarity as they realize their classmates face similar challenges. Additionally, learners can seek support through joining support groups and language clubs, or practice self-talk where they verbalize and imagine the upcoming situation, reassuring themselves that they can handle it despite difficulties.

Implementing Psychological Strategies

Students are recommended to implement psychology-related strategies contributed to their foreign language anxiety. Initially, they must use positive thinking strategy in the classroom. It is demonstrated that when students face with foreign language anxiety in the English classroom, they primarily employ positive coping strategies. These included adopting positive attitudes, being well-prepared, and utilizing extra effort. Additionally, students often use seeking assistance from their peers, particularly when they had difficulty understanding the teacher's explanations (Alrabai, 2015; Marwan, 2016). Also, according to the findings, positive thinking emerged as the most frequently employed coping strategy by participants when facing foreign language learning anxiety. Furthermore, positive thinking was identified as the most influential predictor among all coping variables for reducing the level of foreign language learning anxiety. Conversely, the results indicated that resignation was associated with higher levels of foreign language learning anxiety compared to other coping strategies (Naseem & Khalid, 2010). In addition, students are obliged to use avoidance strategy in the classroom, as (Pappamihiel, 2002; Von Worde, 2003) have conducted studies on students' coping strategies in relation to foreign language learning anxiety. Their

researches specifically focused on teenagers and young adults and found that the most commonly employed coping strategy among learners in this age group was avoidance. Additionally, They identified other frequently used strategies, including pretending that the learner is alone, responding in their native language, expressing themselves through writing, and seeking assistance from friends as intermediaries. Foreign and second language (FL/L2) learning is influenced by various interrelated factors, and FL anxiety is recognized as an important affective strategy in the language learning process (Brown, 2000). The affective approach aims to reduce the negative experiences associated with learning a foreign language and encompasses various therapeutic techniques. These techniques include systematic desensitization (Fuller, 1978; Kráľová & Sorádová, 2015) , biofeedback (Walton, 1981), support groups (Horwitz & Young, 1991), relaxation (Ratanasiripong et al., 2010), meditation (Highet, 2015), engagement programs (Ismail, 2016), doodling (Siagto-Wakat, 2017), and recall techniques (Cinkara, 2016). These approaches aim to address and alleviate FL anxiety, fostering a more positive language learning experience.

Finally, students are advised to remove their personal apprehension so that they can English language effectively. In order to overcome their fears, students should begin by identifying the factors that provoke their anxiety and then engage in suitable tasks that can help reduce their stress levels (Bledsoe & Baskin, 2014). They can employ learning strategies like perseverance (continuing despite difficulties), skill development (enhancing speaking abilities, for example), positive thinking (including positive self-talk), compensation strategies, and relaxation techniques to cope with anxiety. By implementing these strategies, students can actively address their apprehensions and cultivate a greater sense of self-assurance (Woodrow, 2006). Among learning strategies, researcher suggest that use of affective and relaxing strategies in the classroom. Nevertheless, very limited number of research conducted on the role of family in reducing student foreiong langauge anxiety that A balanced approach is recommended when it comes to parents' involvement in their children's EFL (English as a Foreign Language) learning. While some argue that parents should closely monitor and support their children's learning to foster focus, others believe that excessive pressure can lead to stress. A fair solution entails parents applying appropriate levels of pressure that encourage their children to learn without overwhelming them. However, this approach presents its own challenges for parents (Ismail, 2016).

Conclusion

In conclusion both teachers and students play important role in eradctin foreong langauge anxieyt. Teachers play a crucial role in reducing foreign language anxiety among EFL learners through various strategies. They can use diverse classroom activities such as drama, role play, language-related games, and group work to create an engaging and less stressful learning environment. Implementing student-centered learning approaches, such as cooperative learning and collaborative learning, can also help alleviate anxiety by promoting student engagement and interaction. Clear instruction, personalized instruction, and adapting speech to students' levels can further reduce anxiety. Creating a relaxing classroom environment, with proper seating arrangements and a friendly atmosphere, can contribute to a positive learning environment. Teachers should also address students' psychological aspects by providing support, motivation, and strategies to overcome anxiety. Additionally, technology can be utilized, such as social media, video recording, computerized

pronunciation practices, and virtual platforms, to enhance language learning and reduce anxiety. On the other hand, students play a crucial role in reducing foreign language anxiety when learning English as a second or foreign language. They can take proactive steps to identify and address their personal and interpersonal anxieties within the classroom. Techniques such as expressing fears, discussing them with peers, and seeking support through support groups or language clubs can help students realize they are not alone in their anxiety and create a sense of solidarity. Moreover, employing positive thinking strategies, seeking assistance from peers, and utilizing coping strategies can significantly reduce foreign language learning anxiety. Students should also be aware of the avoidance strategy and aim to overcome it by engaging in suitable tasks and implementing effective learning strategies like perseverance, skill development, positive thinking, compensation strategies, and relaxation techniques. By actively addressing their fears and cultivating self-assurance, students can enhance their language learning experience. While the role of families in reducing foreign language anxiety has received limited research attention, it is recommended that parents adopt a balanced approach in supporting their children's language learning, avoiding excessive pressure while still encouraging their progress. Overall, empowering students and providing them with effective strategies and support systems are key elements in minimizing foreign language anxiety and fostering a positive learning environment.

Suggestions for Future Researches

Based on this review paper, following future researches can be conducted:

1. Examine the impact of the teacher-student relationship on foreign language anxiety. Investigate how teachers' supportive and empathetic behaviors, communication styles, and feedback strategies contribute to creating a safe and nurturing learning environment that reduces anxiety and enhances language learning.
2. Explore the integration of technology, such as virtual reality, artificial intelligence, and online platforms, in reducing foreign language anxiety. Investigate how these technological tools can create immersive and interactive learning experiences that alleviate anxiety and enhance engagement. Assess the effectiveness of these interventions compared to traditional classroom methods and identify best practices for implementing technology in anxiety reduction strategies.

Recommendations

Based on the evidence found from this paper, following recommendations are provided for teachers' role in eliminating foreign language anxiety among EFL learners:

1. Implement various activities, such as drama, role plays, language games, and group work, to engage students and create a supportive and non-threatening environment for language learning.
2. Adopt student-centered learning approaches, such as cooperative learning and collaborative learning, where students actively participate, interact with peers, and take responsibility for their learning. These approaches can reduce anxiety and enhance language skills.
3. Give clear instructions for tasks and activities, personalize instruction by using students' names, and adjust the language level to match students' abilities. Clear instructions help students understand tasks and reduce anxiety about making mistakes.
4. Arrange the classroom seating and layout to promote interaction among students and create a sense of belonging. Foster a friendly and supportive atmosphere

where students feel comfortable making mistakes and taking risks in their language learning.

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